

Additional information on the Jackson's long bodied lynx spider *Oxyopes jacksoni* Lessert, 1915 from South Africa (Araneae: Oxyopidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Oxyopes jacksoni* Lessert, 1915, an African endemic species, was described from Tanzania. Since then, it has been recorded from Botswana, Malawi, South Africa and Zimbabwe. The species, a typical plant dweller, is also sampled from the ground layer. Very little has been published on the species, and here, notes on their morphology, based on live photographs, are provided, along with a discussion on their feeding behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Oxyopes* Latreille, 1804, is represented by 286 species, of which about 74 are known from Africa and 26 from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Members of the *Oxyopes* genus occur in high numbers in the field and are commonly found on vegetation. Many species were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) surveys, mainly by sweeping and beating the vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

In this paper *Oxyopes jacksoni* Lessert (1915), an African endemic species described from Tanzania is discussed. Since then, it has been recorded from Botswana, Malawi, South Africa, and Zimbabwe (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). Based on live photographs, information on their general morphology and colour variation is provided, along with notes on their lifestyle, feeding behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC). Some of the photographs requested for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) are shown here. Additional information from pictures taken by the public, deposited in iNaturalist, was exported from <https://inaturalist> on May 30, 2025.

TAXONOMY

Oxyopes jacksoni Lessert, 1915

Oxyopes jacksoni Lessert, 1915: 470 (mf); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 548; 2020: 27-28; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2023: 169.

Diagnosis: Size: TL female and male 5-8 mm. This species is recognised by its long body. The general colour varies from greyish white (Fig. 1), to creamish brown (Figs 2 & 3), to darker brown (Figs 10 & 11). The body is decorated with several longitudinal bands over the carapace and abdomen (Fig. 1). On carapace a median band is present bordered by two thin white bands on both sides, followed by broader dark bands on both sides and a narrow band around the border (Figs 2 & 3); the same pattern extends over the abdomen. It also extends over the clypeus (Fig. 10). Legs all the same colour, faintly mottled (Fig. 10). Male (Fig. 3) resembles female (Fig. 2) but sometimes slightly darker. *Oxyopes* species possess cuticular scales, which are flattened setae that vary in shape and colour; in *O. jacksoni*, the scales found on the body are lanceolate (Fig. 9) and spatulate on the legs (Fig. 10). The scales are easily lost.

Figures 1–3. *Oxyopes jacksoni*. 1. Female from Centurion, dorsal view. 2–3. Showing difference between female (2) and male (3). Credits: 1. Cecile Roux. 2 & 3. Peter Webb.

Figures 4–10. *Oxyopes jacksoni*. 4–5. Drawing male palp. 6. Palp ventral view. 7–8. Epigyne. 9. Male carapace showing the scales. 10. Female anterior view showing the clypeus. Credits: 4, 5, 7. After Lessert (1915). 6 & 8. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 9 & 10. Peter Webb.

Carapace: longer than wide, high and convex anteriorly, sloping posteriorly; clypeus wide; eight eyes occupying a small area on edge of carapace (Fig. 10); eyes form a hexagon with posterior row slightly procurved and anterior row strongly recurved. Abdomen long oval tapers to a point posteriorly. Legs are long and slender with prominent spines; leg IV is longer than leg III. Male palp large (Figs 4-6) with cymbium having a posterior bulge; epigyne as seen in Figs 7 & 8.

LIFESTYLE

Oxyopids, known as lynx spiders, thrive in grassy fields, leafy vegetation, and shrubs. *Oxyopes jacksoni* is very common on vegetation and occurred in high numbers on grasses, but they have also been sampled from the ground layer. They prefer warm, open habitats for hunting prey rather than relying on webs. Unlike web-building spiders, lynx spiders are active hunters, relying on their speed and excellent vision to ambush prey.

They catch prey with their legs by jumping a few centimetres into the air to seize a passing insect in full flight; others execute short jumps in pursuit of prey. Observations also indicate that they will stretch themselves out on the surface of a leaf to drop on moths and wasps flying beneath the leaf. The egg cocoons are fastened to a twig or leaf, and the female guards and defends the eggs.

Their presence in grasslands, shrublands, and agricultural landscapes maintains ecological balance by controlling flies, aphids, and other small arthropods. *Oxyopes jacksoni* was also commonly found in agroecosystems. As part of SANSA (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013), it was sampled from cotton (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999), citrus and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001) and maize and sunflowers fields.

Oxyopes jacksoni was also observed on the ground layer, frequently between leaf litter. However, the second author made some interesting observations, having witnessed the species ambush prey on buffalo dung (Figs 15–17), sometimes with as many as three individuals per dung pat. They lie in ambush on the surface of the dung, capturing flies and other insects that visit it. This behaviour is illustrated in Fig. 17, where one is seen feeding on a fly attracted to the dung. However, what is interesting is that the white colour of the spider stands out clearly against the dark-coloured dung. The species is also now reported from buck dung (Figs 13 & 14) as well as hyena dung.

Figures 11–17. *Oxyopes jacksoni*. 11. Male. 12. Female from Tswalu Nature Reserve. 13–14. Female on buck dung. 15–17. Females on buffalo dung showing it feeding on a fly. Credit: 11–12. Peter Webb. 13–14. Ross Hawkins. 15–17. Andrew Deacon.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Malawi and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION OF *OXYOPES JACKSONI* IN SOUTH AFRICA

SANSA SURVEYS: The distribution of *O. jacksoni* as shown in Fig. 18 were sampled during SANSA surveys and specimens were recorded from all the provinces but absent from the Eastern Cape the North West with single records from the Western and Northern Cape. The completed locality data set can be viewed on Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020.

Figure 18. Distribution records of *Oxyopes jacksoni* in South Africa. Showing the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist "Research Grade" observations of *O. jacksoni* exported from <https://www.inaturalist> on 01 June 2025.

Explanatory note: Although species identifications on iNaturalist rely mostly on the often doubtful recognition of live specimens from photographs, some spider species, such as *Oxyopes jacksoni*, present distinctive colour patterns, body shape, and other morphological characters that allow identification from photographs with reasonable certainty when using the relevant SANSA Photo ID Guide (in this case: Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). The authors support the identifications of the "Research Grade" iNaturalist observations of *O. jacksoni* whose locations are provided here. The citizen science observations provide a useful additional perspective on the species' distribution pattern in South Africa. Of note here, is the iNaturalist observations in the Eastern Cape.

HABITAT

Oxyopes jacksoni was sampled from vegetation in the Forest, Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013); and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011). An iNaturalist observations suggests Albany Thicket as well.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

As part of the SANSA we determine the conservation status of

species and it was important to know where spider species already receive some protection. *Oxyopes jacksoni* have been recorded from 80 protected areas of which several have been published. In the SAN parks the species was recorded Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024). In the Free State it was recorded from Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2013) and in Gauteng from the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2024). In KwaZulu-Natal they were sampled from Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010). In Limpopo from the Blouberg Nature Reserve; Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.* 2008); Makalali Nature Reserve Western Soutpansberg (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

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